

Flemichapparin—A, a new Chalcone from *Flemingia chappan* Ham

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The occurrence of 2',4'-dihydroxychalcone in the whole plant of *Flemingia chappan* and the isolation and structure elucidation of a new chalcone designated as flemichapparin from the same source have formed the subject matter of two earlier communications^{1,2}. Further investigation on the same plant has led to the isolation of another new chalcone named flemichapparin-A in poor yield for which we propose the structure (I).

STRUCTURE-I

Flemichapparin-A crystallises from benzene as bright red needles, m.p. 192°, and analyses for the molecular formula $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ (M^+322); ν_{max} ($CHCl_3$) 3540 cm^{-1} (—OH), 2990 cm^{-1} (—CH), 1640 cm^{-1} (chelated $>C=O$), 1620, 1600, 1575, 1480 cm^{-1} (aromatic), 1400 and 1380 cm^{-1} (gem-dimethyl); λ_{max}^{MeOH} (ϵ) 2250 (23506), 300 (35400), 322 (sh) (25760) and 355 $m\mu$ (21574). Colour tests (negative Shinoda and positive $SbCl_5$ reaction) restricted the assignment to chalcone or aurone classes.

The N.M.R. spectrum (60 Mc/sec. in $CDCl_3$ with TMS as internal standard) shows two *trans*-olefinic protons at 8.0 δ (a) (doublet, $J = 15$ c/s) and 7.56 δ (b) (doublet, $J = 15$ c/s) providing evidence for the chalcone system^{3,5}. The two phenolic protons (c) and (d) appear as sharp singlets at 13.3 and 5.15 δ (disappear on D_2O exchange) respectively indicating that only one —OH (13.3 δ) is *ortho* to the carbonyl group. The presence of two *ortho* —OH groups should have given rise to a less sharp band at higher field (10.4–11 δ)⁴. Two olefinic protons at 6.8 (e) and 5.62 δ (f), each appearing as a doublet ($J = 10$ c/s), and two tertiary methyls (g) (6 H, 1.5 δ) define the presence of a chromene ring^{3,5}. Five aromatic protons (i) merging with two olefinic protons (—CH = CH— *trans*) appear as a multiplet around 7.35–7.80 δ along with a sharp one proton aromatic singlet at 7.4 δ .

The mass spectrum of flemichapparin-A exhibits, besides the molecular ion peak at m/e 322, a number of prominent peaks. The significant ion fragments with their probable structural assignments⁶ are shown in Scheme I.

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Scheme 1

The unsubstituted nature of the A ring is clearly indicated by the presence of peaks at m/e 245 (M-77) and m/e 218 (M-104) corresponding to loss of phenyl group and a neutral styrene molecule, respectively, from the molecular ion. This confirms that out of the eighteen protons of flemichapparin-A, seven only reside in the cinnamoyl portion, and the remaining eleven protons are present on ring B. The assignment of ten protons on ring B has already been provided (two phenolic -OH, two tertiary methyls and -CH = CH- of the chromene ring). It only remains now to place one aromatic proton on ring B. The N.M.R. spectral data suggest 2,4,5-aromatic substitution pattern³ on ring B. The sharp singlet (h) due to the single aromatic proton on ring B appears at 7.4 δ which is a strong evidence that it experiences the deshielding effect of the adjacent carbonyl group, together with the shielding effect of one -OH in *ortho* position and also excludes the possibility that it lies between two oxygens thereby ruling out the usual phoroglucinol substitution pattern.

The co-occurrence of flemichapparin², a congener chalcone of *Flemingia chappar*, having similar type of aromatic substitution pattern on ring B as flemichapparin-A, lends further support for the proposed structure (I). Further chemical as well as synthetic evidences to confirm the structure of flemichapparin-A are now under way.

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